

App Design, Architecture, and Development Plan

Deliverable D3.1

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Acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
EC	European Commission
WP	Work Package
ToC	Table of Contents
EC	European Commission
EU	The European Union
WP	Work Package
API	Application Programming Interface
DTLF	Digital Transport and Logistics Forum
B2A	Business to Administration
B2B	Business to Business
REST	Representational State Transfer
RPC	Remote Procedure Call
SOAP	Simple Object Access Protocol
protobuf	protocol buffer
XML	Extensible Markup Language
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
YAML	Yet Another Markup Language
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
RSS	Really Simple Syndication
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
HTTPS	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
JWT	JSON Web Token
OAS	OpenAPI Specification
TIS	Technology Independent Service
IAA	Identification, Authentication, and Authorization
UML	Unified Modeling Language

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1. Executive Summary

The KEYSTONE project aims to take a significant evolutionary step in the intermodal transport sector by creating an advanced digital ecosystem.

KEYSTONE stands for “Knowledgable comprEhensive and fully integrated SmarT sOlutioNs for rEsilient, sustainable and optimized transport operations”. KEYSTONE is a HORIZON Research and Innovation Action (Call: HORIZON-CL5-2022-D6-02, Topic: HORIZON-CL5-2022-D6-02-03) and has received funding from the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101103740. The project duration is 36 months, effective from 1st of June 2023 and the end date is 31st of May 2026. The Granting Authority is the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (DG CINEA1), under the powers delegated by the European Commission.

A significant focus of this project is the design of the software architecture. This includes a comprehensive low-level architecture that details the server configurations and the mapping of software deployment.

Deliverable 3.1 encompasses the app design, architecture, and development plan. This document is the output of Task 3.1, whose goal is to design an app architecture that ensures a secure and accessible application, based on the comprehensive research and guidelines provided by Work Package 2, and the gap analysis conducted in Task 1.3.

To ensure high usability across multiple devices for a limited-scale pilot, serve drivers, enforcement personnel, and logistics managers, ensure security, and enhance and foster collaboration with key logistics stakeholders, the app architecture presented in this deliverable includes a robust back-end platform where documents and data can be securely stored¹ and exchanged. The KEYSTONE platform is designed to meet stringent security requirements, thus ensuring that all data is protected against unauthorized access and security breaches. The server infrastructure is meticulously planned to support, in a hypothetical future scenario, not only the application's requirements, but also a solid mechanism of load balancing, the possibility to add redundancy, and failover mechanisms to ensure uninterrupted service. The architecture is designed to ensure scalability and high performance, also after the end of the Project..

In addition to the architectural design, the document also establishes a clear roadmap for the development. This roadmap outlines the key milestones and deliverables, ensuring that the project stays on track and meets its deadlines.

In conclusion, the app architecture presented in D3.1 aims to provide a secure, accessible, and user-friendly solution that meets the needs of all stakeholders. By leveraging the research and guidelines from Work Package 2 and addressing the gaps identified in Task 1.3, we have created a comprehensive plan that will guide the development and deployment of the KEYSTONE application, ensuring its success in the pilot phase and beyond.

¹ In case of asynchronous communication with the external systems.

2. Introduction

2.1 Background

In the realm of European transport and logistics, the necessity for data-driven operations cannot be overstated. Real-time analysis and visualization of data concerning vehicles, drivers, and transported goods are pivotal for optimizing operations and ensuring compliance. However, the progress in this domain is hindered by various challenges, including legacy systems, fragmented data, capability gaps, and obstacles to data sharing. Addressing these challenges head-on, the project Knowledgeable comprehensive and fully integrated Smart solutions for resilient, sustainable and optimized transport operations (KEYSTONE) has emerged with a bold vision.

KEYSTONE seeks to contribute to a roadmap for the digital transformation of the European transport ecosystem by introducing standardized, truly Plug-and-Play solutions that bridge existing gaps, irrespective of legacy systems. This initiative marks a significant advancement in ongoing efforts to foster data-driven capabilities within transport operations. KEYSTONE is designed to integrate existing data-driven platforms, services, and skill development solutions across a diverse spectrum of European stakeholders.

Beyond technological advancements, the project also places emphasis on providing policy recommendations to alleviate shortages in data literacy and digital leadership. By fostering collaboration among regulators, operators, and service providers, KEYSTONE aims to harness the power of data for compliance purposes effectively.

Deliverable 3.1, the App Design, Architecture, and Development Plan, is crucial to the actual realization of the KEYSTONE project's objectives. Unifying transport data across Europe is challenging and requires an App design tailored to ensure the highest usability across various devices. The web application should be accessible not only via mobile devices but also through laptops and tablets, ensuring flexibility and convenience for all users. This makes it suitable for the limited-scale piloting activities to be rolled out in the final stage of the KEYSTONE project.

The application has to be intended to serve multiple user groups, including drivers, enforcement personnel, and logistics managers. Drivers could use the app both before and during their trips to ensure compliance and efficiency. Enforcement personnel at crossings and checkpoints could utilize the app to verify compliance and streamline their operations. Additionally, logistics managers can track the compliance of their drivers in real-time, enhancing overall operational oversight and efficiency.

The approach employed ensures that the application can be easily scaled and maintained, reducing downtime and improving reliability.

2.2 Objectives of the Deliverable 3.1

T3.1 aims at designing an app architecture capable of ensuring a secure and accessible application. The KEYSTONE application will be accessible via handheld devices as well as PC desktops, thus ensuring the highest usability across devices for a limited scale pilot. Drivers, both before and during trips, as well as enforcement personnel at crossings and check points, and logistics managers (to track the compliance of their drivers) will be able to use the application. The objectives of Deliverable 3.1 aligns with the goals of the project as follows:

- Propose an integrated approach to favour the collaboration between different stakeholders of the logistics sector. By identifying the data sources and thus the stakeholders which will provide the data for a limited scale pilot, D3.1 provides an app architecture which ensures the inclusion of the key stakeholders of the logistics sector.
- Develop an API standardization that implements Plug-and-Play design principles and the federative infrastructure of platforms and logistics. D3.1 presents an app architecture that guarantees interoperability and continuity of the services among the different systems throughout Europe.

In summary, Deliverable 3.1 presents the KEYSTONE app design, the technologies identified for its development, the reasons behind such choices, and the development plan.

2.3 Overview of the connections with the other WPs

Deliverable 3.1, “App Design, Architecture, and Development Plan”, is connected to other work packages and tasks within the KEYSTONE project. These dependencies are crucial to the design of the app, as they allow for taking informed decisions in the identification of the technological stack to be employed. The Gap Analysis and State of the Art conducted in Work Package 1 (WP1) as well as the research and guidelines provided by Work Package 2 (WP2) served as the basis for the design choices presented in this document.

More specifically:

- **Task 1.1 - Stakeholders' Definition and Needs Analysis:** This task focuses on mapping and analyzing stakeholders, their needs, regulations, and challenges related to the deployment of a digitalized transport ecosystem. The outcomes of Task 1.1, documented in Final Output D1.1: Stakeholders' identification and needs (Sabino Metta, 2023), provide valuable insights into the requirements and expectations of stakeholders regarding data exchange and interoperability, allowing for the appropriate architectural choices in D3.1, in order to address the identified needs and challenges of the key stakeholders.
- **Task 1.2 - State of the Art Analysis and Requirement Generation:** Task 1.2 involves understanding the current state of the art in transport operations and capturing requirements for the KEYSTONE solutions through focus groups. The final output of this task, D1.2: Focus groups report including stakeholder requirements and expectations (Alexeis Garcia-Perez, 2024), includes stakeholders' requirements and expectations, which are crucial to the design of the app. D3.1 ensures adherence to the stakeholders requirements by ensuring usability across multiple devices and all the identified target users. The inventory of existing solutions performed in Task 1.2 is functional to the identification of the gaps between the different competing offers, thus making it possible to define new functionalities or else combine useful functionalities for a simple, yet comprehensive platform design in Task 3.1.
- **Task 1.3 - Study of Existing Digital Platforms and Gap Analysis:** Task 1.3 conducts an in-depth analysis of existing digital platforms and identifies gaps between stakeholders' needs and current platform capabilities. The findings from this task, documented in Final Output D1.3: Needs and requirements for the future digital logistics ecosystems (Camille Leotta D. M., 2024), provide insights into the requirements for the future digital logistics ecosystem. These insights are pivotal for the design of the App in D3.1, ensuring to provide the basis for a proper blueprint for seamless data exchange and interoperability.
- **Task 1.4 - Digital Ecosystem private and public perspectives:** This task, starting from the identification of the different needs of the public and private sector in transport, finally generated use cases derived from transport ecosystems, to define the interface and functionality of the KEYSTONE Digital Ecosystem. Task 1.4 outcomes are instrumental to understanding the technological stack needed for fulfilling the expected functionalities within the KEYSTONE Digital Ecosystem.
- **Task 2.1 - Plug and play implementation framework; the API reference model:** The output of Task 2.1, the “API Reference Model”, described within D2.1, is a pivotal component as providing a structured framework for API standardization facilitates seamless data exchange among diverse stakeholders. The design of the REST services within T3.1 required a tight collaboration between these two tasks, as well as between T3.1 and T2.2 and T2.3, as reported below.
- **Task 2.2 - Retrieving and sending enforcement data with the API Reference Model:** Task 2.2 builds upon the API Reference Model created in Task 2.1 to focus on retrieving and sending enforcement data. It elaborates on specific parts of the model, such as interconnectivity with other platforms, information retrieval based on legislative requirements, and information exchange between vehicles and platforms. The design of the KEYSTONE App in Task 3.1 progressed with a closed collaboration with Task 2.2 to ensure the required interconnectivity with external systems would be possible, facilitating secure communication and interoperability within the transport ecosystem.

By leveraging the outputs and insights from these tasks within both WP1 and WP2, Deliverable D3.1, “App Design, Architecture, and Development Plan”, is developed with a comprehensive understanding of stakeholder needs, state-of-the-art practices, existing platform capabilities, the broader digital ecosystem context, and related research and guidelines. Due to this connections, D3.1 aligns with project objectives and contributes effectively to the digital transformation of the European transport ecosystem envisioned by the KEYSTONE project.

T3.1 and its output, the “App Design, Architecture, and Development Plan” presented in this document, provides valuable input to other WP and tasks in the KEYSTONE project:

- Task 2.3 – Develop the API standard. This task will develop an implementation library written in Python using the reference model of T2.1 and tackling the connections of T2.2. The library will include a set of APIs for retrieving and sending information between 3rd party applications and the app developed in WP3: as such, a tight collaboration between the design of the app and the development of the API standard is necessary.
- Task 3.2 defines the Interface (UIUX) according to the raw data available in the database and the process data coming from the business layer. A joint design effort between the API, the backend and the UIUX responsables was required to agree on the data set that finally shaped the UIUX.
- Task 3.3 - Embedding cyber security in the KEYSTONE solutions: Task 3.3 will ensure that key cyber security controls are embedded in the KEYSTONE solutions, the architecture of which is designed within Task 3.1. The output of Task 3.1 defines the components of the system which Task 3.3 will protect against cyber security threats; moreover, users must be able to exchange documents securely by design, that is, by the architectural choices made within Task 3.1.
- Task 3.4 – Development of a web app: the connection of Task 3.1 with Task 3.4 is the strongest among all, as Task 3.4 requires the design of the app carried out within Task 3.1 in order to make it possible to develop the App itself.
- Work Package 4 (WP4) - Piloting: WP4 focuses on piloting the solutions developed within the KEYSTONE project in real-world scenarios, as per the use cases outlined in D1.4 and consequently in D4.2.. The App designed within T3.1 will be used during the WP4 pilots.

3. Literature review

3.1 Web Applications

In this section we explore various web application architectures, their components, and the advantages of modern web architecture. The review covers several common architectures:

- **Monolithic Architecture:** This straightforward method constructs the entire application as a unified entity, offering simplicity in development and deployment but posing challenges in scalability.
- **Client-Server Architecture:** This architecture partitions the application into the client (user interface) and the web server (handling data and logic), improving scalability compared to monolithic setups.
- **Microservices Architecture:** This approach breaks the application into smaller, independent services that communicate via APIs, facilitating scalability, maintenance, and fault tolerance.
- **Service-Oriented Architecture:** This architecture assembles the application from a series of services with distinct functionalities, offering high scalability and flexibility but can be complex to develop.
- **Event-Driven Architecture:** This design responds to events such as user actions or data changes, allowing high scalability and responsiveness but requiring expertise in event-driven design.

Among these, the Microservices Architecture has important characteristics in its capability to divide the application into small, independent services, each with its function, communicating via APIs. This architecture offers flexibility, fault tolerance, and scalability, fitting the project's needs better.

Web architectures operate through client-side and back-end code. Client-side code, written in HTML, JavaScript, and CSS, handles user inputs and creates the visual elements. Back-end code, written in languages like Java, C#, Node.js, and Python, manages the application's logic, processes user requests, and communicates with databases.

The 3-tier architecture is highlighted as a modern approach, splitting the application into three layers: Presentation Layer (User Interface), Application Layer (Business Logic), and Data Layer (Database). This architecture enhances scalability, flexibility, and maintainability.

The advantages of modern web architecture lies in the enhancement of security, authentication, user experience, automation, speed, reliability, scalability, and error logging. These features are crucial for developing robust, user-friendly, and efficient web applications.

3.2 Client Side

The client side encompasses the development platforms, frameworks, and architectures used to create modern, responsive, and efficient web applications.

Modern web applications leverage the capabilities of contemporary browsers, utilizing HTML5, CSS3, and JavaScript to handle display, rendering, navigation, data entry, and validation tasks. Once the application is loaded in the browser, REST APIs facilitate communication with the server to manage data operations necessary for business workflows.

3.2.1.1 Available Frameworks

Several frameworks are popular for client-side web application development.

- **Angular:** Developed by Google and released in 2010, Angular is a TypeScript-based framework designed for building complex, reactive UIs, primarily for Single Page Applications (SPAs). It features

two-way data binding, MVC architecture, dependency injection, and a Command Line Interface (CLI) for project management.

- **React:** Created by Facebook in 2011, React is a JavaScript library for building user interfaces. It uses a component-based architecture, a virtual DOM for performance optimization, JSX syntax, one-way data binding, and supports native mobile application development through React Native.
- **Vue:** Released in 2014 by a former Google employee, Vue aims to combine the best aspects of Angular with custom tools. It is known for its simplicity, flexibility, reactivity system, single file components, and official libraries for routing (Vue Router) and state management (Vuex).

3.2.1.2 Architecture

The architecture of web applications significantly impacts their performance and user experience. Two prominent architectures are discussed:

Single-Page Application (SPA)

SPAs load all content on a single page, dynamically updating content as users navigate. This approach improves response times and navigation speed, offering a seamless user experience. SPAs use JavaScript, HTML, and CSS for the frontend, with frameworks like React, Angular, and Vue being popular choices. The backend can be implemented in any language, provided it supports REST APIs to deliver necessary content.

Advantages:

- Agile and fluid navigation with minimal waiting times.
- Reduced server resource usage, beneficial for slow internet connections.
- Simplified web analytics and lower server costs.

Disadvantages:

- Potentially slower initial load times for large websites.
- Security concerns due to client-side source code exposure.
- SEO challenges, as search engines may struggle to index content not immediately visible.

Progressive Web Applications (PWA)

PWAs combine the features of web apps and native applications, offering offline mode and enhanced user experience. They use service workers to handle user requests, data synchronization, and offline access. PWAs have demonstrated significant business value, increasing user engagement and improving mobile user experience.

3.3 Backend Side

This section of the literature review focuses on the backend components of web applications, detailing their architectures, databases, and server technologies.

Backend components are responsible for receiving, processing, and responding to client application requests. They manage business logic, validate user requests, and handle data storage and retrieval from database servers.

The choice of backend development tech stack, including programming languages, frameworks, and tools, depends on the type and functionality of the web application.

3.3.1.1 Architectures

Microservices

Microservices architecture is a popular approach for building highly scalable web applications.

It is based on decentralization and modularity, breaking the system into independent microservices, each handling a specific business function.

This architecture offers high reliability, scalability, and agility but can be complex to develop, test, and support compared to traditional monolithic architectures.

Monolith

Monolithic architecture is the simplest approach, building the application as a single unit that runs all functions. Monoliths can be faster to design, develop, test, and deploy, making them suitable for MVPs and small projects.

However, they are harder to scale and modernize, as changes affect the entire system, complicating error tracing and troubleshooting.

Serverless

Serverless architecture involves deploying applications on external servers managed by cloud service providers like AWS, Google Cloud, and Microsoft Azure.

This model allows organizations to delegate infrastructure management and benefit from a pay-as-you-use pricing structure. It is ideal for companies lacking in-house expertise or seeking to reduce support costs.

3.3.1.2 Databases

Databases are organized collections of structured information, managed by database management systems (DBMS). They have evolved from early hierarchical and network databases to modern relational, object-oriented, and NoSQL databases. Today, cloud databases and self-driving databases offer advanced capabilities for data collection, storage, management, and utilization.

The main types of databases we analysed are:

- **Relational Databases:** Organize data in tables with rows and columns, providing efficient access to structured information.
- **Object-Oriented Databases:** Represent data as objects, similar to object-oriented programming.
- **Distributed Databases:** Consist of multiple files located in different sites, offering redundancy and improved access.
- **Data Warehouses:** Central repositories designed for fast query and analysis.
- **NoSQL Databases:** Handle unstructured and semi-structured data, popular for complex web applications.
- **Graph Databases:** Store data in terms of entities and relationships.
- **Cloud Databases:** Reside on cloud platforms, available in traditional and Database as a Service (DBaaS) models.
- **Document Databases:** Store data in JSON format, offering flexibility for modern applications.

3.3.1.3 Web Servers

Web servers use HTTP to serve files that create web pages in response to client requests.

They are always connected to the internet and have unique IP addresses, allowing hosting providers to manage multiple domains on a single server.

3.3.1.4 Application Servers

Application servers host applications or software that deliver business applications through communication protocols.

They provide a service layer model with software components accessible via an API, often including features like clustering, fail-over, and load-balancing to ensure high availability and scalability.

4. KEYSTONE solution

4.1 Overview

This chapter details the part corresponding to the design and development of the Web application (WP3) where both the server part and the client part will be explained.

4.2 Backend

4.2.1 Overview

The backend of a system like KEYSTONE represents the heart of the technological infrastructure and simultaneously provides the functionalities that the frontend exposes to end users.

In fact, it is responsible for data management, request processing, and integration with other systems and services. All operations are ensured in their efficiency, security, and scalability.

4.2.2 Software architecture

4.2.2.1 Overview

It is possible to identify the main software components of the KEYSTONE backend:

- **REST Services:** These are the external interface of the APIs. They feed the web app and all systems (which we will call consumers) that consume the data that KEYSTONE possesses or simply conveys. They provide data in a format that represents the standard model of KEYSTONE.
- **Database:** KEYSTONE embraces the policy of allowing third-party systems to submit their data whenever they deem it most appropriate. This necessitates saving the data on internal databases. Specifically, the possibility of interacting with a multitude of interlocutors, who will therefore submit data using many different technologies and formats that are extremely heterogeneous, creates the need for a sort of data lake where raw data can be channeled. Naturally, the need for data standardization and real-time retrieval pushes for structuring and inserting the data into a relational database.
- **API (Application Programming Interface):** APIs allow communication between the backend and other systems or services. In the case of KEYSTONE, they are exposed and invoked through a set of REST services and access third-party systems using a middleware layer that acts as a connector and remaps data coming from outside into the model we have chosen as the standard for KEYSTONE.
- **Connectors:** In KEYSTONE, there is a need to interface and obtain data from many systems that may present such data in formats and through technologies that are extremely different. The possibility of having standardized data within KEYSTONE provides the opportunity to use a single interface and implement ad hoc connectors for the system we need to interface with.
- **DAO (Data Access Object):** The layer that allows access to the database requires a standardization mechanism at the time of data saving. This ensures that data is structured in already standardized databases when it needs to be read.

All this allows us to outline a list of functionalities that the KEYSTONE backend will cover and provide. To summarize:

- **Request Management:** The backend receives and handles requests from the frontend, the web app, or from third-party systems, processing them and returning appropriate responses (standardized and aggregated data).
- **Data Processing and Transformation:** In all the operations that KEYSTONE performs and for all the functionalities that KEYSTONE exposes, there are validation, standardization, and/or data aggregation operations.
- **Integration with Third-Party Systems:** The backend integrates with various external services provided by different stakeholders, and this can and should be done using connectors or providing functionalities through the exposure of REST services.

We will go to use a component diagram to clearly and schematically visualize the external systems with which the system will interact, its databases, and its main software components. Subsequently, we will visualize and schematize in a detailed architecture all the main software components that will be developed.

Figure 1 Software Architecture diagram

So, we can go to describe each component, part of the detail design of the backend, except for the APIs, which definition is argument of the Deliverable 2.3.

4.2.2.2 REST services definitions

KEYSTONE's REST services represent the way KEYSTONE interfaces with the external world. As illustrated in Figure 9, the external world refers not only to third-party systems that require KEYSTONE's data but also, and especially, to the web app, which allows users to access KEYSTONE's data.

The choice of REST technology as an interface to the external world is evident in its distinctive characteristics.

- **Accessibility and Ease of Use:** REST services are based on standard protocols like HTTP. This makes them easily accessible and usable by any client that supports these protocols. In this way, KEYSTONE can interact with a wide range of platforms, web applications, mobile applications, or other server systems. Since no special configuration is required to use REST services, ease of use and integration is prioritized.
- **Scalability:** REST services are designed to be stateless, meaning that each client request to the server must contain all the information necessary to understand and process the request. This approach simplifies system scalability, as the server does not need to maintain session state between requests.
- **Flexibility and Modularity:** REST services offer great flexibility, allowing only the necessary resources to be exposed and to grow as needs increase. This is fundamental in KEYSTONE, which starts with a prototyping phase and limited interactions, with the ambition to become a reference point in the dialogue between actors in cross-border intermodal transport. The system architecture can be organized modularly, allowing new functionalities to be developed and implemented without negatively impacting the existing system.
- **Improved User Experience:** From the user interface perspective, REST services enable the creation of responsive and dynamic web applications. Data can be loaded partially, increasing fluidity and interactivity during application use.

In summary, using REST services as an interface to the external world and the user interface of a system offers advantages in terms of scalability, flexibility, and improved user experience, making them the ideal choice.

The top-down approach requires, first and foremost in this initial phase of the project, the development of functionalities that produce the data exposed by the front end of the web application.

Modularity and scalability will allow, in a second phase of the project, to approach the system design in a reverse manner, by bottom-up, and expose the basic components of the APIs through REST services. This will facilitate the potential integration of third-party systems that wish to implement their own interface to KEYSTONE, to expose KEYSTONE's data using their own aggregation logic and possibly their own user interface.

Tables where to find a synthetic description of each service are reported in Section 4.3.2.2 REST services definitions.

4.2.2.3 Interface for connectors

First of all, this solution allows for the centralization and standardization of how KEYSTONE APIs interact with various third-party systems, whether they are data providers in synchronous mode or our internal database for data submitted in asynchronous mode.

A single interface allows for the implementation of an abstraction layer that isolates KEYSTONE APIs from the specific details of each external system, making the code more modular and reusable.

Another crucial aspect is that a single interface for connectors to external systems promotes continuous integration and code reuse. Developers can work on new integrations, starting from a code structure that has already been used for other integrations.

This approach reduces the time-to-market for new integrations.

Furthermore, the potential addition of new features becomes somewhat more easily extendable to all connectors with external systems, improving the overall quality of the software.

In summary, adopting a single interface to implement all connectors to external systems is a strategic choice that offers significant advantages in terms of maintenance, consistency, and development agility.

However, at the current state of the art, KEYSTONE APIs are still under development, so the definition of the common interface is deferred to a greater level of detail and a subsequent phase of design.

4.2.3 Hardware architecture

4.2.3.1 Overview

Defining hardware architecture driven by software architecture means designing and organizing the physical components of a computer system in a way that effectively supports the needs and functionalities of the software.

This process begins with a thorough analysis of the characteristics that the system must provide through its software architecture, carefully evaluating the system's workloads, the number of users it must serve, the amount of data it must store over time, and the response speed it must guarantee to a user.

Therefore, if we wanted to outline the main characteristics through which we must ensure that the system meets operational and performance requirements, here is what we need to consider:

- **Processor (CPU):** The sizing of the processor is fundamental as it determines the system's processing capacity. It is essential to consider both the number of cores and the clock speed based on the expected workloads.
- **Memory (RAM):** The amount of RAM (Random Access Memory) directly affects the system's ability to handle simultaneous applications and processes. It is crucial to size the RAM according to the needs of the applications and the number of users expected to access the system simultaneously.
- **Storage (Disc Free):** The data storage capacity must be evaluated, in the case of KEYSTONE, based on how many asynchronous systems it interfaces with and, of course, on the size of the records that will be stored for each system over time.

Obviously, in this initial prototyping phase, which only encompasses a single asynchronous system and will have a limited number of users involved in test scenarios, the values of RAM and especially the storage space sizing will not be of vital importance.

What becomes a key point of sizing, however, is the ability to scale it according to the needs of potential production deployment in a real environment. This capability is known as scalability.

The hardware architecture must be designed to grow and adapt to future needs.

This can mean the ability to add additional servers (if necessary), increase storage capacity, or RAM without having to redesign the system. Virtualization and the use of cloud technologies can play an important role in this context, allowing resources to be dynamically allocated based on needs.

In the following diagram, it appears how all the components of the system will be distributed among the servers.

Figure 2 Components diagram of the hardware architecture

4.2.3.2 Components and sizing

To provide an overview of the server sizing for KEYSTONE and the technology stack used as the runtime environment for the application, particularly its backend, we will insert the configuration parameters of the various servers into corresponding tables.

It is worth noting the extensive use of open-source software, a typical choice in research projects, especially considering the prototyping characteristics of the project's initial phase.

This does not preclude the possibility of switching to licensed versions if necessary, as this could be done with very limited effort due to the almost absolute compatibility with them.

Table 1 KEYSTONE Application Server

Application Server		
Technological Stack ²	Operating System	Linux Red Hat
	SDK	Open Java
	Application Server	WildFly open source
Sizing	Disk Space	30Gb

² All latest stable versions.

	RAM	8Gb
Ports and protocols	TCP	Port 80
		Port 443
	SFTP ³	Port 22
	SSH	Port 22

Table 2 KEYSTONE database server

DB Server		
Technological Stack ⁴	Operating System	Linux Red Hat
	Datalake (non relational database)	MongoDB open source ⁵
	Relational Database	MySQL ⁶
Sizing	Disk Space	30Gb + 20Gb ⁷
	RAM	8Gb

4.2.4 Data structure for asynchronous systems

4.2.4.1 Structured Data

The data structure for asynchronous systems is the database mapping of the standard KEYSTONE data structure, used by the KEYSTONE standard APIs.

So, we can refer the Deliverable 2.3 for a detailed description of the process that drove to the final definition of the data structure.

4.2.4.2 Datalake

The need to interface with an increasing number of systems, each characterized by its own communication technology, has led to the requirement for a heterogeneous container to store any type of data format, from CSV to SOAP to JSON.

Specifically, in this initial phase of the project, KEYSTONE needs to interface asynchronously with the TOS of CIM in Novara, which will transmit its data using an sFTP folder.

Nevertheless, it is also conceivable to create a service where files of any type can be submitted, thus providing a simple, flexible, and secure interface.

Regardless of the method used by systems with asynchronous integration to upload data, the heterogeneous nature of incoming documents necessitates the availability of a data lake.

³ Through this port, TOS from Novara will upload EDIGES status files on Keytone's application server.

⁴ All latest stable versions.

⁵ This is the data lake where raw data from asynchronous platforms will flow.

⁶ There probably will be two databases with the same user, one for configuration/users/etc., and one for applicative structured data coming from platforms communicating with KEYSTONE in asynchronous way.

⁷ Space for data that will be saved on the databases.

This system requirement has been met through the use of MongoDB, a document database with an open-source version.

Here it is provided a very basic implementation, which is sufficient for our prototyping needs but already capable of accepting multiple different and distinguishable types through the use of an appropriate naming convention.

Figure 3 Non relational database ⁸

4.3 MoveHub emulator

4.3.1 Overview

Following the in-depth analysis carried out in Task 1.3, the opportunity provided by the MoveHub platform to all member states has emerged, conveying information from the RESPER, TACHONET, ERRU platforms, etc.

On the other hand, MoveHub has a policy whereby the data it conveys can only be provided to the member states of the European Community. Therefore, in Deliverable 2.2, a door remains open to possible alternatives, such as the use of a mockup system.

In fact, data related to licenses, professional certifications, sanctions, driving time violations as recorded by the tachograph, etc., are important, if not essential, for KEYSTONE. For this reason, the idea conceived in Deliverable 2.2 to have at least a mockup system to emulate MoveHub data has materialized as the most realistic option given the current state of the art.

This platform is therefore the subject of this part of the Deliverable. Naturally, the mockup system that we will design, which provides data emulating those from MoveHub, while having characteristics entirely comparable to those of KEYSTONE, is appropriately scaled down in some of its parts, as will be detailed further in the document.

4.3.2 Software architecture

⁸ In the figure the use in this first phase of the project is reported, i.e. as container for the EDIGES XML status files.

4.3.2.1 Overview

The usual component diagram will clearly and schematically visualize the simple software architecture, appearing the most standard as possible.

A little MySQL relational database for containing the data from MoveHub, is present on the application server. To complete the technological landscape, a set of REST services will be exposed for accessing the different type of data.

Figure 4 Movehub - mockup system

4.3.2.2 REST services definitions

The system that emulates MoveHub is considered in every way as an external system from which to draw the necessary data.

In this case, the system is provided with the most basic REST services possible. Specifically, these are all and only those that provide the data that KEYSTONE in turn exposes externally and particularly to its own web application.

Therefore, in many cases, they are nothing more than a kind of replica of the services that KEYSTONE itself exposes. Naturally, much of what is requested by the KEYSTONE web application from the backend has the

vehicle's license plate as an input parameter, while in this case, the same functionalities are exposed starting from the natural keys that identify the data on the mockup. Let's see how.

Tables where to find a synthetic description of each service are following but, for a more detailed description, see the YAML files in attachment.

REST services are grouped by type of data that they manage: driver data and truck data.

Driver Data Services

Table 3 Services - Get driver license data

Get driver license data	
path	/driverdata/license/{countrycode}/{eid}
parameters	Country Code
	eID
response	Driver Name
	Driver Fiscal Code
	Check Datetime
	Driver License

Table 4 Services - Get driver professional qualification certificate data

Get driver professional qualification certificate data	
path	/driverdata/pdqcc/{countrycode}/{eid}
parameters	Country Code
	eID
response	Driver Name
	Driver Fiscal Code
	Check Datetime
	Professional Driver Qualification Certificate

Table 5 Services - Get driver tachograph data

Get driver tachograph data	
----------------------------	--

path	/driverdata/tachograph/{countrycode}/{eid}
parameters	Country Code
	eID
response	Driver Name
	Driver Fiscal Code
	Check Datetime
	Driving Exceeding Time Limits

Table 6 Services - Get driver traffic violation data

Get driver traffic violation data	
path	/driverdata/trafficviolation/{countrycode}/{eid}
parameters	Country Code
	eID
response	Driver Name
	Driver Fiscal Code
	Check Datetime
	Traffic Violation

Truck Data Services

Table 7 Services - Get truck owner data

Get truck owner data	
path	/truckdata/owner/{countrycode}/{platenumber}
parameters	Country Code
	Plate Number
response	Country Code
	Plate Number
	Owner

Table 8 Services - Get truck inspection service data

Get truck inspection service data	
path	/truckdata/inspection/{countrycode}/{platenumber}
parameters	Country Code
	Plate Number
response	Country Code
	Plate Number
	Dates List

Table 9 Services - Get truck insurance data

Get truck insurance data	
path	/truckdata/insurance/{countrycode}/{platenumber}
parameters	Country Code
	Plate Number
response	Country Code
	Plate Number
	Is Insured
	In Date
	Expiration Date
	Company Name
	Insurance Number

4.3.3 Hardware architecture

4.3.3.1 Components and sizing

To configure this server, we used a technology stack identical to the one used for configuring the two KEYSTONE servers (application and database).

Since this server is used only as a mockup for data that we cannot obtain from MoveHub but that KEYSTONE needs and must consume, it is not subject to significant load and only needs to receive REST calls from KEYSTONE. It has been slightly downsized compared to KEYSTONE's parameters.

Notably, the application and data have not been placed on the same server, as there is no need for it.

Table 10 Services - MoveHub mockup Server (application and database)

Mockup Server		
Technological Stack ⁹	Operating System	Linux Red Hat
	SDK	Open Java
	Application Server	WildFly open source
	Relational Database	MySQL ¹⁰
Sizing	Disk Space	30Gb
	RAM	4Gb
Ports and protocols	TCP	Port 80
		Port 443
	SFTP	Port 22
	SSH	Port 22

4.3.4 Data structure

4.3.4.1 Overview

Guided by the data that MoveHub consolidates, transmitting it to and from all systems that adhere to the sharing network, three different schemas have been defined. Each schema represents and contains data respectively related to licenses, the tachograph, and, lastly, trucks.

4.3.4.2 Driver licenses

The data structure related to licenses is intrinsically linked to professional driving certifications, as professional certification cannot be issued without a valid license to which it is associated. This is why we find information on both within the same schema, which also includes information on penalties. Penalties can include suspensions or revocations of the license, logically grouping them together.

⁹ All latest stable versions

¹⁰ The relational database for mockup data to emulate data coming from MoveHub or from another platform exposing the data from Driver Licences, Plate Licences, Tachograph, etc.

Figure 5 Driver licenses data

4.3.4.3 Tachograph data

The tachograph data reveals the driving and rest periods of each driver. There are restrictions on the hours of driving that can be performed within the same day, the same week, and the same two consecutive weeks. Therefore, any breaches of these limits are saved in the appropriate table.

Figure 6 Tachograph data

4.3.4.4 Truck data

The data related to the truck is stored in the corresponding schema. This schema contains information on ownership, insurance, and inspections in their conventional sense.

Figure 7 Truck data

4.4 Frontend

Here it is presented the rationale for the technological choices and architecture decisions to support the front end making. Angular is the choice as a development framework capable of meeting the UI/UX and technological requirements as well. For the UI/UX, FIGMA was selected as sketching tool for its direct compatibility during the coding process.

4.4.1 Technology

Angular is a popular open-source framework developed by Google for building dynamic and feature-rich web applications. It provides a robust platform for developing scalable, maintainable, and high-performance applications. Angular offers numerous benefits that make it an excellent choice for web application development.

In Table 11 is an overview of Angular's key features.

Table 11 Angular - Key features

Feature	Description
Component-Based Architecture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promotes modularity by dividing the application into reusable, testable, and independent components. Facilitates code reuse and ease of maintenance.
Two-Way Data Binding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensures automatic synchronization between the user interface (UI) and the underlying data model. Simplifies the development process by reducing the need for manual DOM manipulation.
Built-in Tools and Features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Offers features like forms, routing, and HTTP client out of the box. Provides directives (e.g., *ngIf, *ngFor) for DOM manipulation without relying on external libraries.
Dependency Injection (DI)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Simplifies the management of services and dependencies across components. Enhances scalability and improves code maintainability.
TypeScript Integration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Angular is built with TypeScript, which provides: Static typing to catch errors at compile time. Advanced tooling for debugging and refactoring. Enhanced readability and code quality.
Routing and Navigation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Angular Router enables seamless navigation within single-page applications (SPAs).
RxJS for Reactive Programming	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Facilitates handling asynchronous data streams effectively.
Built-in Directives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Angular provides structural and attribute directives to manipulate DOM elements dynamically.
High Performance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ahead-of-Time (AOT) Compilation: Pre-compiles templates and components for faster load times and better performance. Lazy Loading: Loads modules on demand, optimizing resource usage and improving the app's speed.

Strong Community and Ecosystem	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Backed by Google, ensuring regular updates, long-term support, and reliability. • Large community and ecosystem provide access to extensive libraries, tools, and tutorials.
Cross-Platform Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitates the creation of web, mobile, and desktop applications using a single framework. • Angular Universal supports server-side rendering (SSR) for better SEO and faster initial load times.
Testing-Friendly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Angular provides built-in support for unit testing and end-to-end testing through Jasmine, Karma, and Protractor. • Modular architecture allows easy isolation and testing of components and services.
Scalability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Designed for building large-scale applications with multiple developers. • Features like modules and lazy loading make Angular apps easily scalable.
Security	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Offers built-in protection against common vulnerabilities such as XSS (Cross-Site Scripting). • Supports Content Security Policies (CSP) and best practices to enhance application security.
Consistent Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Angular CLI standardizes project creation, development, and deployment. • Ensures consistency across the development team, leading to improved collaboration.

Advantages of Angular

The key advantages of adopting Angular are the following:

- Comprehensive ecosystem with tools for every development phase.
- Strong community support and extensive documentation.
- Regular updates and long-term support from Google.
- High performance with Ahead-of-Time (AOT) compilation.
- With its robust features, scalability, and community support, Angular is a powerful framework suitable for building modern and complex web applications.

With its robust features, scalability, and community support, Angular is a powerful framework suitable for building modern and complex web applications.

4.4.2 Architecture

Angular's architecture is based on a component-based design that promotes modularity and scalability. It follows the Model-View-Controller (MVC) or MVVM (Model-View-ViewModel) pattern, providing a structured way to build dynamic, single-page applications (SPAs). In Table 12 is an explanation of the core building blocks and how they interact with one another.

Table 12 Core building blocks of Angular's architecture

Building block	Description
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Modules	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Angular applications are modularized using NgModules, which group related components, directives, pipes, and services. The root module is the AppModule, which bootstraps the application. Additional feature modules (e.g., UserModule, AdminModule) are used to organize and encapsulate functionalities. Modularization facilitates lazy loading and improves scalability.
Components	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Components are the building blocks of the UI. Each component consists of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> HTML Template: Defines the structure and layout. TypeScript Class: Contains the logic and data binding. CSS/SCSS Styles: Manages the appearance. Components use decorators (e.g., @Component) to link templates and metadata.
Templates	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Define the UI layout using HTML and Angular-specific directives (e.g., *ngIf, *ngFor). Bind data using data binding techniques: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interpolation: {{ data }} Property Binding: [property]="expression" Event Binding: (event)="handler(\$event)" Two-Way Binding: [(ngModel)]="data"
Directives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Extend HTML by adding custom behavior to elements. Types of directives: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Structural Directives: Modify DOM structure (e.g., *ngIf, *ngFor). Attribute Directives: Change the appearance or behavior of elements (e.g., ngClass, ngStyle). Custom Directives: User-defined directives for specific functionality.
Services and Dependency Injection (DI)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Services are used to manage business logic, share data, and interact with external resources (e.g., APIs). Dependency Injection provides an efficient way to inject services into components and other services.
Routing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Angular Router enables navigation and URL management in SPAs. Routes are defined in app-routing.module.ts and map paths to components. Supports advanced features like lazy loading, route guards, and child routes.
Pipes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Transform data in templates for display purposes (e.g., uppercase, date, currency). Custom pipes can be created for specific transformations.
Modules for HTTP and Observables	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The HttpClientModule provides tools for making HTTP requests and interacting with RESTful APIs. RxJS Observables handle asynchronous data streams, enabling powerful reactive programming capabilities.

Table 13 Flow of Angular Architecture

Element	Description
Bootstrap Module	The application starts with the AppModule, which bootstraps the AppComponent (root component).

Component-Driven UI	The root component serves as the entry point, and child components are rendered based on the template structure.
Data Binding	Components bind data to the UI using Angular’s binding techniques, ensuring automatic synchronization between the model and the view.
Routing and Navigation	The Angular Router handles SPA navigation, loading different components or modules dynamically based on the URL.
Service Interaction	Components interact with services to fetch or modify data. Services use the HttpClient module to make API calls.
Dependency Injection	Services are injected into components or other services using Angular’s DI system, ensuring reusability and modularity.
Change Detection	Angular’s change detection system ensures the UI is updated automatically when data changes.

In Figure 8 a diagram representing the usage of Angular’s components within the KEYSTONE project is reported.

Figure 8 Angular and KEYSTONE Interface (UI)

4.4.3 UI/UX

The web app aspect driven by the UI/UX design, was covered using FIGMA tool for sketching. This allows a direct conversion of visual aspects and functionalities into coding. There is a dedicated task T3.2 for the UI/UX definition that feeds into T3.1, hence we are not extending this section as it is fully covered in D3.2

Figure 9 FIGMA sketches used to drive the implementation of the web app

5. Development Plan

While the Design of the KEYSTONE App started in November 2024, its development starts in January 2025 and ends in May 2025, with testing activities to be completed by June 2025, as illustrated in the comprehensive Gantt shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10 Design, Development, and Testing of the KEYSTONE App (along with the timelines of D3.1 and D3.4, the WP3 deliverables focused on the design and the development of the KEYSTONE App, respectively)

The activities included in the Gantt are the following:

1. Frontend
 - 1.1. Technology Design
 - 1.2. API Integration
 - 1.2.1. Swagger Documentation
 - 1.2.2. Library
 - 1.2.3. Design Iterations (starting in January and April 2025, respectively)
 - 1.3. UI/UX Integration
 - 1.3.1. Technology Design (Workshop Outcome)

- 1.3.2. Wireframe Sketch
- 1.3.3. Design Iterations (starting in January and April 2025, respectively)
- 2. Backend
 - 2.1. Design
 - 2.1.1. Software Architecture
 - 2.1.2. Low Level Architecture
 - 2.1.3. Sizing
 - 2.1.4. Data Structure
 - 2.1.5. KAPIs REST
 - 2.2. Development
 - 2.2.1. Data Structure
 - 2.2.2. DAO Layer
 - 2.2.3. MoveHub Mockup (Data Structure, Mapping, DAO, BI, REST)
 - 2.2.4. Business Logic Layer
 - 2.2.5. Data Migration SFTP-Data Pool-SQLDB
 - 2.2.6. KAPIs REST (KEYSTONE Standard API)
 - 2.2.7. Design Iteration
- 3. Testing
 - 3.1. Internal Testing
 - 3.2. Test to completion (until June 2025)

6. Conclusions

This document provides a comprehensive overview of the design and development of a secure and accessible web application, following the guidelines and research from Work Package 2 and the gap analysis conducted in Task 1.3. The introduction outlines the background, objectives, methodology, expected outcomes, KPIs, milestones, and connected work packages/tasks, setting the stage for the detailed analysis that follows.

The literature review covers both web applications and client-side technologies, examining various web application components, types of web architecture, and modern web app architecture. It also explores client-side frameworks such as Angular, React, and Vue, highlighting their features and architectural styles, including Single-Page Applications (SPA) and Progressive Web Applications (PWA).

On the backend side, the review delves into different architectures like microservices, monoliths, and serverless models, as well as database technologies and their evolution. It also discusses the roles of web servers and application servers in supporting web applications.

The KEYSTONE solution section presents an in-depth analysis of the server-side and client-side components of the proposed application. It details the software and hardware architecture, data structures for asynchronous systems, and the MoveHub emulator. Additionally, it addresses user cases, security, authentication, and user options by roles. In the following Section 6.1 we provide a summary of the resulting design.

Overall, the document provides a detailed roadmap for the development of the KEYSTONE application, ensuring that all aspects are thoroughly planned and executed. The findings emphasize the importance of a robust and scalable architecture, the use of modern frameworks and technologies, and a comprehensive development and testing plan to ensure the application's success.

6.1 KEYSTONE App design overview

6.1.1 Server side

6.1.1.1 Backend Architecture

The backend of a system like KEYSTONE represents the core of the technological infrastructure, providing functionalities that the frontend exposes to end users. It is responsible for data management, request processing, and integration with other systems and services, ensuring efficiency, security, and scalability.

6.1.1.2 Software Architecture

The main software components of the KEYSTONE backend are:

- **REST Services:** These are the external interface of the APIs, feeding the web app and systems that consume KEYSTONE's data.
- **Database:** KEYSTONE allows third-party systems to submit data, which is saved in internal databases. Data is structured in a relational database for standardization and real-time retrieval.
- **API:** APIs enable communication between the backend and other systems, exposed through REST services and using middleware to map external data to KEYSTONE's standard model.
- **Connectors:** These interface with various systems, standardizing data for use within KEYSTONE.
- **DAO (Data Access Object):** This layer allows database access, ensuring data standardization at the time of saving.

6.1.1.3 Backend Functionalities

The backend functionalities can be schematized by these following points:

- **Request Management:** The backend receives and handles requests from the frontend, web app, or third-party systems, returning appropriate responses.
- **Data Processing and Transformation:** Includes validation, standardization, and aggregation of data.
- **Integration with Third-Party Systems:** Integrates various external services using connectors or exposing functionalities through REST services.

KEYSTONE's REST services represent how KEYSTONE interfaces itself with the external world, including third-party systems and the web app.

The main advantages of using REST services are:

- **Accessibility and Ease of Use:** Based on standard protocols like HTTP, making KEYSTONE accessible and usable by any client supporting these protocols.
- **Scalability:** Designed to be stateless, simplifying system scalability.
- **Flexibility and Modularity:** Allows exposure of only necessary resources and growth as needs increase.
- **Improved User Experience:** Enables the creation of responsive and dynamic web applications.

The initial top-down approach involves developing functionalities that produce data exposed by the web app frontend. Modularity and scalability will allow for a reverse approach in later stages, exposing the basic API components through REST services.

6.1.1.4 Hardware Architecture

Defining hardware architecture based on software architecture involves designing and organizing the physical components of a computer system to effectively support the software's needs and functionalities. This process starts with a thorough analysis of the system's requirements, including workloads, user capacity, data storage needs, and response speed.

Key characteristics to ensure the system meets operational and performance requirements include:

- **Processor (CPU):** The processor's size is crucial as it determines the system's processing capacity. Both the number of cores and clock speed must be considered based on expected workloads.
- **Memory (RAM):** The amount of RAM affects the system's ability to handle simultaneous applications and processes. It should be sized according to the application's needs and the number of users.
- **Storage:** Data storage capacity must be evaluated based on the number of asynchronous systems interfaced with and the size of records stored over time.

In the initial prototyping phase, involving a single asynchronous system and a limited number of test users, RAM and storage space are less critical.

However, scalability is essential for potential production deployment. The hardware architecture must be designed to grow and adapt to future needs, allowing for additional servers, increased storage, or RAM without redesigning the system. Virtualization and cloud technologies can dynamically allocate resources based on needs.

To provide an overview of server sizing for KEYSTONE and the technology stack used as the runtime environment, configuration parameters of various servers are detailed in corresponding tables. The extensive use of open-source software is typical in research projects, especially in the prototyping phase. Switching to licensed versions is possible with minimal effort due to compatibility.

6.1.1.5 Datalake

The need to interface with numerous systems, each with its own communication technology, requires a heterogeneous container to store various data formats, from CSV to SOAP to JSON. In the initial project phase, KEYSTONE interfaces asynchronously with the TOS of CIM in Novara, transmitting data via an sFTP folder. A service for submitting files of any type is also conceivable, providing a simple, flexible, and secure interface.

The heterogeneous nature of incoming documents necessitates a data lake, fulfilled by MongoDB, an open-source document database. This basic implementation is sufficient for prototyping needs and capable of accepting multiple distinguishable types through appropriate naming conventions.

6.1.2 MoveHub Emulator

The MoveHub platform offers member states access to data from various systems like RESPER, TACHONET, and ERRU.

However, MoveHub's policy restricts data access to European Community member states.

Therefore, Deliverable 2.2 suggests using a mockup system to emulate MoveHub data, which is crucial for KEYSTONE. This mockup system is the focus of this section.

The software architecture includes a MySQL database on the application server and a set of REST services for data access.

The mockup system provides basic REST services to emulate MoveHub data, replicating the services KEYSTONE exposes. These services are grouped by data type: driver data and truck data.

The server uses a technology stack similar to KEYSTONE's servers but is downsized.

It runs on Linux Red Hat, with Open Java SDK, WildFly application server, and MySQL database.

The server specifications include 30GB disk space and 4GB RAM.

Three schemas are defined for data related to licenses, tachographs, and trucks.

- **Driver Licenses:** This schema includes data on licenses, professional certifications, and penalties.
- **Tachograph Data:** This schema records driving and rest periods, including any violations.
- **Truck Data:** This schema contains information on truck ownership, insurance, and inspections.

6.1.3 Front end

Angular is the choice as a development framework, as it is capable of meeting the UI/UX and technological requirements as well. For the UI/UX, FIGMA was selected as sketching tool for its direct compatibility during the coding process.

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